

Chemical speciation of some divalent transition metal ion complexes of L-ornithine in low dielectric media

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Abstract : The stability constants binary complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with L-ornithine in 0–60% v/v dioxan-water mixtures were determined pH-metrically at 303 K and at an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L^{-1} . The existence of various binary complexes was established from modeling studies using computer program MINQUAD75. The best fit chemical models containing ML, ML_2 , MLH and ML_2H_2 species were arrived at based on statistical parameters. The trend in the variation of stability constants with the medium composition was explained on the basis of changes in the dielectric constant of the solution. Effect of errors in concentrations of the ingredients on stability constants was also studied. Chemical speciation is discussed based on the distribution diagrams, drawn using HYSS HYPERQUAD.

Keywords : Binary complexes, stability constants, L-ornithine, speciation, dioxan.

Introduction

Speciation study of essential metal ion complexes is useful to understand the role played by the active site cavities in biological molecules and the bonding behavior of protein residues with the metal ion. Hence, the chemical speciation of biologically important ligands with some essential and toxic metal ions has been studied in this laboratory^{1–5}. They can be used to mimic metalloproteins⁶. L-Ornithine (Orn), in mammals, forms precursor for synthesis of L-arginine. In human colon carcinoma cells, L-arginine is the common precursor of Orn, which regulates arginase activity in the liver. Feeding of adults with ornithine increases the total strength and lean body mass, and decreases urinary hydroxyproline. Ornithine can be used in combination with manganese to achieve hypoglycemia in hyperglycemic conditions. Hyperornithinaemia-hyperammonaemia-homocitrullinuria syndrome is caused by mutations in a gene encoding mitochondrial ornithine transporter⁷.

Cobalt is an essential trace element for all multicellular organisms at the active center of cobalamins⁸. Nickel is an essential nutrient. It is a component of urease and hydrogenase^{9,10}. Copper is an essential element for life and it has antibacterial properties¹¹. Congenital inability

to excrete copper can result in toxic levels of copper accumulation, which leads to Wilson's disease^{12,13}.

Dioxan (Dox) is a water miscible non-polar organic solvent¹⁴. The Dox-water mixtures are the combination of aprotic and protic solvents with wide range of dielectric constants and with good solubility for polar as well as non-polar solutes. The co-solvent-induced increased basicity of Dox-water mixtures increases the stabilization of the protons. It is primarily used as a solvent in the manufacturing sector, but is also found in fumigants and automotive coolant. It is also a contaminant in cosmetics and personal care products such as deodorants, shampoos, toothpastes and mouthwashes. Hence, the results of a speciation study on the interaction of Orn with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in Dox-water mixtures are reported in this paper.

Results and discussion

The best fit models that contain the stoichiometry of the complex species and their overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 1. The possibility of formation of polymeric complexes is excluded as the ratio of Total ligand (TL0) to Total metal (TM0) is 2.5–5.0, as given in "Experimental". Also the presence of dimeric and trimeric

Table 1. Parameters of best fit chemical models of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} binary complexes of Orn in Dox-water mixtures

% v/v Dox	log β_{mlh} (SD)				NP	U_{Corr} $\times 10^8$	χ^2	Skewness	Kurtosis	<i>R</i> -Factor
	ML	ML ₂	MLH	ML ₂ H ₂						
	Co ^{II} (pH 2.9–11.0)									
0.00	5.86(8)	8.72(2)	14.02(9)	27.53(12)	59	2.53	11.53	-0.19	3.02	0.0133
10.00	6.06(5)	8.92(10)	14.09(7)	27.28(5)	53	2.56	22.62	-0.84	4.26	0.0012
20.00	6.93(10)	9.01(9)	14.25(6)	27.50(7)	40	1.33	28.37	0.03	3.33	0.0049
30.00	7.33(11)	9.29(7)	14.42(8)	27.53(8)	48	0.06	24.96	-0.13	5.25	0.0086
40.00	7.46(6)	9.67(8)	14.50(4)	27.55(11)	45	1.92	22.02	-0.7	2.42	0.0150
50.00	7.86(12)	9.89(8)	14.66(10)	27.82(3)	57	2.33	3.32	-0.33	3.63	0.0076
60.00	7.92(7)	9.95(10)	14.73(5)	27.97(6)	43	0.90	21.0	0.01	3.09	0.0143
	Ni ^{II} (pH 2.9–9.0)									
0.00	7.68(9)	13.09(17)	15.21(7)	29.31(7)	73	3.24	29.70	-0.16	3.72	0.0139
10.00	8.42(10)	14.00(9)	15.10(9)	29.28(2)	48	1.23	26.64	0.03	5.22	0.0091
20.00	8.54(3)	14.14(10)	15.14(6)	29.63(9)	72	1.08	19.11	-1.35	4.69	0.0055
30.00	8.57(10)	14.14(6)	15.27(9)	29.69(4)	60	0.07	47.78	-0.34	6.09	0.0045
40.00	8.69(2)	14.15(3)	15.42(6)	29.79(9)	81	0.49	14.16	-0.50	3.06	0.0070
50.00	8.71(9)	14.24(5)	15.46(14)	29.81(5)	90	4.44	26.18	0.04	3.59	0.0116
60.00	8.89(6)	14.58(8)	15.76(2)	29.95(2)	85	1.82	44.82	-1.27	3.04	0.0022
	Cu ^{II} (pH 1.9–10.0)									
0.00	12.71(13)	15.79(4)	17.91(11)	34.42(5)	67	1.13	13.00	-0.37	3.17	0.0123
10.00	12.01(2)	17.21(7)	19.00(8)	34.13(11)	44	1.63	13.34	0.79	4.06	0.0069
20.00	12.14(9)	17.33(8)	19.67(2)	34.16(0)	100	1.05	24.59	1.12	3.16	0.0043
30.00	12.40(8)	17.40(2)	20.03(3)	34.29(8)	83	2.25	19.00	-0.03	5.42	0.0090
40.00	12.66(6)	17.55(3)	20.15(12)	34.40(2)	105	1.74	19.45	-0.75	1.87	0.0065
50.00	12.81(11)	17.79(13)	20.24(9)	34.62(8)	49	1.22	14.58	-0.36	4.58	0.0027
60.00	12.97(9)	17.94(4)	20.35(6)	34.73(6)	95	3.48	12.01	-0.14	3.70	0.0089

species is ruled out since the concentration of L-ornithine is very dilute (0.05 mol L⁻¹ in aqueous solution).

The formation constants for different metal ions were found to obey the Irving-William order^{15,16}. Very low standard deviation in overall stability constants log β signifies the precision of these constants. The small values of U_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ligand and hydrogen ion at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom, small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems are validated by the residual analysis¹.

In data analysis with least squares methods, the residuals (the differences between the experimental data and the data simulated based on model parameters) are assumed to follow Gaussian distribution. When the data are fit into the models, the residuals should ideally be equal to zero. If statistical measures of the residuals and the

errors assumed in the models are not significantly different from each other, the model is said to be adequate. Further, a model is considered adequate only if the residuals do not show any trend. Respecting the hypothesis that the errors are random and follow normal distribution in the least squares analysis, the residuals are tested for normal distribution. Such tests are χ^2 , skewness, kurtosis and *R*-factor. These statistical parameters show that the best fit models portray the metal-ligand species in Dox-water mixtures, as discussed below.

χ^2 distribution measures the probability of residuals forming a part of standard normal distribution with zero mean and unit standard deviation. If the χ^2 calculated is less than the table value, the model is accepted. Hamilton's *R*-factor ratio test is applied in complex equilibria to decide whether inclusion of more species in the model is necessary or not¹⁷. The low crystallographic *R*-values given

in Table 1 indicate the sufficiency of the model. The values of skewness are between -1.35 and 1.12. These data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution and hence, least-squares method can be applied to the data. Kurtosis is a measure of the peakedness of the error distribution near a modal value. For an ideal normal distribution kurtosis value should be three (mesokurtic). If the calculated kurtosis is less than three, the peak of the error distribution curve is flat (platykurtic) and if the kurtosis is greater than three, the distribution shall have sharp peak (leptokurtic). The kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals form leptokurtic pattern in majority of the systems.

Interpretation of systematic errors :

In order to rely upon the best chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the influential parameters like concentrations of alkali, mineral acid, ligand, metal and log *F* (Table

Table 2. Effect of errors in influential parameters on Co^{II}-Orn complex stability constants in 10% v/v Dox-water mixture

Ingredient	%	log β _{mlh} (SD)			
		ML	ML ₂	MLH	ML ₂ H ₂
	0%	6.06(5)	8.92(10)	14.09(7)	27.28(5)
Alkali	-5	Rejected	Rejected	8.95(19)	30.14(11)
	-2	4.54(33)	7.94(27)	Rejected	27.15(37)
	2	7.43(25)	11.20(12)	15.36(28)	28.33(12)
	5	9.44(32)	14.20(17)	16.26(36)	29.13(39)
Acid	-5	9.15(33)	13.87(19)	17.21(35)	29.44(39)
	-2	7.39(25)	10.16(10)	15.63(26)	28.55(34)
	2	Rejected	9.99(18)	15.93(30)	30.21(58)
	5	3.769(60)	3.95(98)	16.47(84)	26.35(80)
Ligand	-5	6.48(26)	9.47(11)	14.55(28)	27.22(36)
	-2	6.29(27)	8.99(10)	14.10(26)	27.30(35)
	2	5.92(25)	8.25(11)	14.00(27)	27.30(34)
	5	5.79(26)	7.93(13)	14.18(28)	28.07(27)
Metal	-5	6.09(25)	8.98(11)	14.12(27)	27.31(35)
	-2	6.10(24)	8.17(10)	14.01(26)	27.19(34)
	2	6.10(25)	8.96(10)	14.14(27)	27.30(34)
	5	5.79(26)	7.88(13)	14.15(28)	28.32(34)
log <i>F</i>	-5	6.11(25)	8.89(11)	14.06(27)	27.26(35)
	-2	6.08(24)	8.70(10)	14.16(26)	27.25(34)
	2	6.14(25)	8.95(10)	14.10(27)	27.27(35)
	5	6.13(26)	8.90(11)	14.15(25)	26.20(35)

2). The sensitivity of the stability constants to these errors is in the order : alkali > acid > ligand > metal > log *F*. Some species were even rejected when errors were introduced in the concentrations. The rejection of some species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors confirm the appropriateness of the experimental conditions (concentrations of ingredients) and choice of the best fit models. This study also indicates the relative sensitivities of the model parameters.

Effect of dielectric constant of medium :

The linear variation log β values with variation of 1/*D* (*D* is the dielectric constant of the medium) of Dox-water mixtures (Fig. 1) indicates that the electrostatic forces are dominating the equilibrium processes of complex formation under the experimental conditions. This linear increase indicates the dominance of the structure-forming nature of Dox over the complexing ability.

Distribution diagrams :

Orn has one dissociable proton and two amino groups which can associate with two protons. It exists as LH₃²⁺ at low pH and gets deprotonated with the formation of LH₂⁺, LH and L⁻, successively, with increasing pH, in the ranges 1.9–4.1, 1.9–9.8 and above 8.0, respectively. The binary metal-ligand complexes confirmed under the experimental conditions are ML, ML₂, MLH and ML₂H₂ for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in the pH range 3.7–11.0. The protonated forms of species like MLH and ML₂H₂ are prevalent at lower pH. The neutral form of Orn forms unprotonated complexes (ML and ML₂) as shown in the following equilibria :

Fig. 1. Variation of stability constant values of metal-Orn complexes with reciprocal of dielectric constant ($1/D$) of Dox : (A) Co^{II} ; (B) Ni^{II} ; (C) Cu^{II} ; (\blacklozenge) $\log \beta_{\text{ML}}$; (\blacksquare) $\log \beta_{\text{ML}_2}$; (\blacktriangle) $\log \beta_{\text{MLH}}$; (\bullet) $\log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{H}_2}$.

Typical distribution diagrams are shown in Fig. 2 in the pH range 3.7–11.0. MLH species is formed for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} according to equilibria 1 and 2 at low pH and it is deprotonated to ML (equilibrium 6) with increasing pH. ML_2H_2 species is formed as per equilibria 3 and 4. Fig. 2B reveals the simultaneous formation of ML_2H_2 and ML. ML is formed as per equilibria 5 and 6. ML_2 is formed by the deprotonation of M_2H_2 (equilibrium 7) and as per equilibria 8 and 9. But ML_2 is not formed through equilibrium 8 in Cu-Orn system (Fig. 2C).

Structures of complexes :

Although it is not possible to elucidate or confirm the structures of complex species pH metrically, it is possible to postulate structures based on comparison with known structures for related complexes. Literature shows that, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions typically form octahedral complexes, with Cu^{II} normally being Jahn-Teller distorted^{19,20}. Thus octahedral structures have been proposed tentatively as given in Fig. 3. Orn is coordinated to the metal ions as (O, N) donor to form MLH and ML_2H_2 , which have eight-membered rings and protonated α -amino groups (structures A and B). They are deprotonated to form ML and ML_2 (structures C and E) where Orn still acts as (O, N) donor. In the case of ML and ML_2 two structures are possible, based on whether eight or seven-membered ring is formed. According to Baeyer strain Theory²¹ (structure C) may rearrange itself to give Structure D where Orn acts as (N, N) donor through both the amino groups. Similarly, Structure E may rearrange itself to give Structure F.

Experimental

0.05 mol L^{-1} solution of Orn (Merck, India) was prepared in triple distilled deionized water by maintaining 0.05 mol L^{-1} hydrochloric acid concentration to increase the solubility. Dox (AR, E. Merck) was used as received. Hydrochloric acid (Qualigens, India) of 0.2 mol L^{-1} was prepared. Sodium chloride (Merck, India) of 2 mol L^{-1} was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. Solutions of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chlorides (0.05 mol L^{-1}) were prepared by dissolving G.R. grade (E. Merck, Germany) salts in triple distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L^{-1} acid (HCl) to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts. Sodium hydroxide (Merck, India) of 0.4 mol L^{-1} was prepared. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification²². The strengths of alkali mineral acid were also determined using the Gran plot method^{23,24}.

Procedure :

The titrimetric data were obtained by using calibrated ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter (readability 0.01). The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred Dox-

Fig. 2. Distribution diagrams of binary complexes of Orn in 10% v/v Dox-water mixture : (A) Co^{II}, (B) Ni^{II} and (C) Cu^{II}.

water mixtures containing inert electrolyte for several days. The effect of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted for in the form of correction factor. For the determination of stability constants of binary species, initially, strong acid was titrated against alkali at regular intervals to check the complete equilibration of the glass electrode. Then, the calomel electrode was refilled with Dox-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. All the pH metric titrations were performed in medium containing varying concentrations of Dox-water

mixtures (0–60% v/v) at 303.0 ± 0.1 K. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1.0 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 cm³. Titrations with different metal-to-ligand ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75 and 1 : 5.0) were carried out with 0.4 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD²⁵ was used to calculate the correction factor. By using pH metric titration data, the binary stability constants were calculated with the computer program MINQUAD75²⁶ which exploits the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt

Fig. 3. Suggested structures of Orn complexes, where S is either solvent or water molecule and M is Co^{II} , Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} .

algorithm. Species distribution diagrams for all the systems were generated with HYSS HYPERQUAD suite program¹⁸. During the refinement of binary systems, the correction factor and protonation constants of Orn were

fixed. The variation of stability constants with the dielectric constant of the medium was analyzed on the basis of electrostatic/non-electrostatic, solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Conclusion

- (i) Orn forms protonated and unprotonated complexes, viz. CoL, CoL₂, CoLH, CoL₂H₂, NiL, NiL₂, NiLH, NiL₂H₂, CuL, CuL₂, CuLH and CuL₂H₂.
- (ii) The linear variation of stability constants as a function of dielectric constant of the medium indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces. Some species are stabilized due to electrostatic interactions and some are destabilized due to the decreased dielectric constant.
- (iii) The order of ingredients influencing the magnitude of stability constants due to incorporation of errors in their concentrations is alkali > acid > ligand > metal > log *F*.
- (iv) High concentrations of the complex chemical species indicate that metals are more amenable for transportation at biological pH.

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